

Quantum Bound States and Special Relativistic Rest Mass Considerations

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In special relativity, one may apply a Lorentz matrix to a 4-vector. This is a linear operation, so the 4-vector: $(0, 2m_0c)$ is equivalent to the two 4-vectors (pc, m_0c) , $(-pc, m_0c)$. Thus, one may consider, as an example, a rest mass to consist of many different p , $-p$ pairs, with different probabilities, if somehow they are all associated with the same rest mass (i.e. energy), for example. Now, nonrelativistically, $E=pp/2m$, so in order to have all p 's associated with the same energy, one requires a $V_1(p)$ (no x dependence), such that: $pp/2m + V_1(p) = E$ ((1))

One, however, usually has $V(x)$ and the notion of a $mov(x)$ at each x . Here, one considers instead constant p values, but $V(x)$ is still a function of x . Furthermore, one would at least require on average that: $\langle pp \rangle / 2m + V(x) = E$. Thus, each $pp/2m$ is linked with a probability $P_1(p,x)$. If these are orthonormal functions, one may readily obtain ((1)). Now, a constant p is associated with a constant spatial density, but $P(p,x)$ is not a constant.

In the case of a single p value, there is no $V(x)$ and $pp/2m = E$, i.e. there is no average. The $P(p,x)$ function, however, cannot simply vanish in such a case. Given that orthonormality is used to create ((1)) with all $P(p,x)$ present, we note that one has: $\int P(p,x) P(p_1,x) dx = 0$. One may ask: What relevance does $P(p,x)P(p,x)$ (for the same p) have? It is a function of x , but one may force it to match the constant spatial density of a constant p . In other words, $P(p,x)P(p,x)$ would represent a spatial density. Such a consideration, we argue, leads to bound state quantum mechanics, but is rooted in the idea of $p,-p$ pairs leading to an overall rest mass, which is what E is. In other words, for a bound state problem, E becomes part of the rest mass energy of the system which has net momentum of 0.

Special Relativity, Rest Mass and Zero Net Momentum

In special relativity, one employs a linear Lorentz transformation which may act on a rest mass, i.e.

$(0, m_0c) \rightarrow (-p, m_0c/2)$ and $(p, m_0c/2) \rightarrow$ One may have many $\pm p$ pairs ((2))

Thus, a positive and negative p pair each with $.5 m_0 c c$ rest energy transforms overall as $(0, m_0c)$, due to linearity.

One may extend this idea to a system of many $\pm p$ pairs, each of which has the same rest mass (energy) E . The $\pm p$ pairs may have different probability weights.

In general, $E=pp/2m$, nonrelativistically, so one needs a p -dependent potential i.e.

$pp/2m + V_1(p) = E$ ((3))

In a physical problem, however, one often has $V(x)$. In order to create ((3)), one may consider orthonormal probabilities $P(p,x)$. A given constant p has a constant spatial density and so the physical relevance of $P(p,x)$ is not clear at this moment

In a general problem which uses $V(x)$ one has:

$$p^2/2m + V(x) = E \quad ((4))$$

As a result, one should have: $\sum_p p^2/2m P(p,x) = p^2/2m$ ((5))

In other words, $p^2/2m$ becomes an rms average in this picture.

Given the notion of an average, it seems that one must use the orthonormal behaviour of the $P(p,x)$'s in order to produce ((3)).

As a result, $P(p,x)P(p,x)$ becomes a relevant quantity. Even if $P(p,x)$ does not have physical meaning (right away), $P(p,x)P(p,x)$ might. In particular, this might represent the constant spatial density of a particle with a constant p . If that is the case:

$$P(p,x)P(p,x) = \text{constant} \quad ((5a))$$

A real function cannot satisfy ((5)), but a complex one can, i.e.: $P^*(p,x)P(p,x) = \text{constant}$ ((5b)).

This yields: $P(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$. ((6)) (This happens to be the eigenfunction of $-i$ times the translational operator $-id/dx$.)

In other words, one obtains quantum mechanics. The starting idea, however, is the special relativistic notion of rest mass being linked to $+/-p$ pairs, thus E should formally be a rest mass in special relativity which it is, even in the quantum mechanical bound state problem.

We note that formally one may write: $P(p,x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / \{\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)\}$. ((7))

Then: $\langle p^2 \rangle / 2m + V(x) = E$ and multiplying by $\exp(-ipx)$ and integrating, with $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$, i.e. a Fourier series, yields:

$$a(p) p^2/2m + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = a(p) E \quad ((8)) \quad \text{or} \quad V(p) = 1/a(p) \sum_k V_k a(p-k) \quad ((9))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the linearity feature of the Lorentz matrix in special relativity may be a starting point for a quantum bound state. From special relativity, one has the equivalence of $(0, 2m_0 c^2)$ with $(-p, m_0 c^2)$ and $(p, m_0 c^2)$ together. Many $+/-p$ pairs all associated with the same energy, but having probabilities, may represent a rest energy E which Lorentz transforms. Given that $E = p^2/2m$ (nonrelativistically), this implies that: $p^2/2m + V(p) = E$ ((1)). At the same, one usually has a $V(x)$ and $p(x)^2/2m + V(x) = E$. The $+/-p$ scheme should then be associated with

$P(p,x)$ probabilities. If these are orthonormal, one readily obtains ((1)). In such a case, one does not only have $P(p,x)$, but also $P(p_1,x)P(p_2,x)$ which is integrated. For $p_1=p_2$, $P(p,x)P(p,x)$ might be interpreted as spatial density because it may apply to a single particle with only p as well as the bound state scenario. In the case of a single particle with constant p , spatial density is constant in space.. $P(p,x)$ cannot be constant in space, but $P(p,x)P(p,x)$ can if one allows $P(p,x)$ to be complex and uses $P^*(p,x)P(p,x) = \text{constant}$. This leads to the $\exp(ipx)$ probability of quantum mechanics. The starting point, however, was to use $\pm p$ pairs to obtain a rest mass energy, which is what E is. Thus, we argue that there is a direct link between the linearity of the Lorentz matrix in special relativity and quantum bound states.